

ONE , TWO AND A LOT LIGHT REPETITION AGAINST TO LAYERS HAVE THE SUN ELEMENTS MODELING

Alijonov Abbosbek Azizjon o'g'li
Andijan machine building institute

ANNOTATION

The sun elements optical feature determination for intended Adopted PVlight House 's Wafer Ray Tracer module and silicon and GaAs based the sun of the elements optical features was determined . Optimal thicknesses for TiO_2 , SiN_x , Al_2O_3 , SiO_2 , MgF_2 suitable 70 nm, 80 nm, 100 nm, 110 nm and 120 nm respectively and this in thicknesses that's it materials with covered silicon justified the sun of the element photogeneration coefficients suitable 76.43 % , 77.87% , 76.96% , 73.2% and 70.27% respectively equality was determined .

Key words : _ The sun elements , exponential , silicon , Urbah theory , TiO_2 , SiN_x , Al_2O_3 , SiO_2 , MgF_2 , single crystal silicon , light Back to coefficient , Light to return against layers , light break down indicator

The sun elements on the surface back going light the amount reduce for a lot layered optical in terms of acceptable has been systems harvest will be done . of silicon complex light break indicator light wave to the length dependence graph shown in figure 1 . So of silicon maximum light break down indicator is 6.891 ha equal to it is light wave length to a value of 370 nm right will come . light break down of the indicator real part wave 1.665 to 6.891 in the range of 250-370 nm increased , in the range of 370-900 nm while exponential decreases . Also this _ in between average light break down the indicator is 3.9 ha equal to Complex light break down of the indicator abstract part while of silicon swallowing coefficient set gives , just like that light break down indicator Back to coefficient set like

giving Air average light break down indicator together equal to that it was for the air and silicon on the surface light about 40% of its energy quantity back goes _ of materials swallow coefficient Urbah theory or in the experiment determined complex light break down of the indicator abstract part through is determined . of the material swallowing coefficient complex light break down of the indicator abstract part right light wave to the length while reverse proportional is the size .

Picture 1. Single crystal of silicon complex light break down indicator light wave to the length dependence

Above in chapter basically silicon justified the sun of the elements to the surface one layer as coated TiO_2 , SiN_x , Al_2O_3 , SiO_2 , MgF_2 materials the sun of the element optical features effect was studied . Today's in the day one layered no , two and three layered light to return against layers there is the sun elements work coming out [1]. In this main The idea is gradient light break down indicator harvest to do Theoretical in terms of thinking if the air light break down indicator with of silicon light break down indicator The gradient is continuous in the interval light break down to the indicator have from the material if we use the sun of the element light Back to coefficient to 0 % reduce can _ Of course, such a

gradient light is ideal break down to the indicator has material _ not , but so the system one how many of materials to make can _ That's why for , silicon justified the sun of the element surface suddenly more than light to return against layers with is being covered . In this main attention of materials light break down to the indicator is directed . That's why for in picture 2 TiO_2 , SiN_x , Al_2O_3 , SiO_2 , MgF_2 of light break down indicators light wave to the length dependence described _ Theirs all of them in the experiment determined .

Picture 2. Single crystal of silicon complex light break down indicator light wave to the length dependence

Above from the graph the most high light break down to the indicator material with TiO_2 and the most minimal light break down to the indicator and the material has MgF_2 that let's see can _ This graph through given in figure 1 photogeneration coefficient light to return against layer to the thickness dependence to prove can _ That is light to return against optimal layer thickness of the material light break down to the indicator reverse is proportional . A lot layered light to return against layers harvest in doing light break down indicator increased to go in order placing need _ That's why for light break down indicator

sharp difference MgF_2 did and TiO_2 from made $MgF_2/TiO_2/n-Si/p-Si$ (a) and $SiO_2/SiN_x/n-Si/p-Si$ (b) solar of the elements swallowing transition and Back to coefficients light wave to the length dependence shown in figure 3 .

ab

Picture 3 . $MgF_2/TiO_2/n-Si/p-Si$ (a) and $SiO_2/SiN_x/n-Si/p-Si$ (b) structural the sun of the element absorption , transition and Back to coefficients light wave to the length dependence . MgF_2 , TiO_2 , SiO_2 , SiN_x and Si 's thickness suitable 120 nm, 70 nm, 110 nm, 80 nm and 200 μm respectively to equal to

$MgF_2/TiO_2/n-Si/p-Si$ structure swallowing spectrum one layered light to return against to layer have silicon justified the sun from element sharp difference did _ Swallowing coefficient wave in the range of 450-950 nm of length almost one different high the value note did _ But this in between swallowing coefficient one little decreased increase observed and wave at a value of 630 nm relatively lower swallowing to the coefficient achieved _ $SiO_2/SiN_x/n-Si/p-Si$ solar of the element swallowing coefficient while wave in the range of 360-1000 nm of length good to the result to melt and light wave at a value of 820 nm maximum absorption of 98% to the coefficient achieved [2]. light to return against of layers thicknesses from this previous in chapter determined optical to the optimal values of layers equal to by doing is being taken . Figure 4 shows the structure of $MgF_2/Al_2O_3/n-Si/p-Si$ (a) and $MgF_2/SiN_x/TiO_2/n-Si/p-Si$ (b) the sun of the element absorption , transition and Back to coefficients light wave to the length

dependence described _

ab

Picture 4 . $MgF_2/Al_2O_3/n-Si/p-Si$ (a) and $MgF_2/SiN_x/TiO_2/n-Si/p-Si$ (b) structural the sun of the element absorption , transition and Back to coefficients light wave to the length dependence . MgF_2 , Al_2O_3 and Si 's thickness suitable 120 nm, 100 nm and 200 μm respectively to equal to

MgF_2 from organize found $MgF_2/Al_2O_3/n-Si/p-Si$ and $MgF_2/TiO_2/n-Si/p-Si$ solar of the elements light swallow spectrum almost one different only swallowing in the coefficient difference is doing So , two layered light to return against to layer have the sun in the element his swallowing spectrum quality top optical layer swallowing of the coefficient size while bottom optical layer set will give it is TiO_2 _ of light break down indicator Al_2O_3 of light break down from the indicator according to of silicon light break down to the indicator closer therefore for $MgF_2/TiO_2/n-Si/p-Si$ solar of the element swallowing coefficient $MgF_2/Al_2O_3/n-Si/p-Si$ sun from that of the element according to higher it has been . light break down indicators increased to go in the way placed MgF_2 , SiN_x , TiO_2 of materials organize found three layered silicon basic $MgF_2/SiN_x/TiO_2/n-Si/p-Si$ solar of the element swallowing spectrum light wave in the range of 400-930 nm of length an average of 92% organize did _ So , light to return against layers the number gain through swallowing coefficient known wave lengths between maximum in value Immutable holding stand up can _ For example, TiO_2

covered silicon justified the sun 400-600 nm wave in the element length between harvest has been swallowing coefficient sharp decrease his MgF_2 on it and SiN_x to cover through loss can _ And in Table 3 light break down of the indicator to the value of according to harvest to do possible has been two and three layered light break down to the indicator have the sun of the elements photogeneration coefficient given .

Table 1. Dielectrics different combination using harvest done a lot light to return against to layer have the sun of the elements photogeneration coefficient

Structures	Photogeneration coefficient
$SiN_x/TiO_2/n-Si/p-Si$	75.41
$Al_2O_3/TiO_2/n-Si/p-Si$	78.57
$SiO_2/TiO_2/n-Si/p-Si$	81.66
$MgF_2/TiO_2/n-Si/p-Si$	81.06
$Al_2O_3/SiN_x/n-Si/p-Si$	73.42
$SiO_2/SiN_x/n-Si/p-Si$	77.69
$MgF_2/SiN_x/n-Si/p-Si$	76.31
$MgF_2/Al_2O_3/n-Si/p-Si$	72.17
$SiO_2/Al_2O_3/n-Si/p-Si$	70.74
$MgF_2/SiO_2/n-Si/p-Si$	65.68
$MgF_2/SiN_x/TiO_2/n-Si/p-Si$	78.63

In the table given to values according to the most good to the system have the sun element is $SiO_2/TiO_2/n-Si/p-Si$ and his photogeneration the coefficient is 81.66% equality was determined . Most bad the result and $MgF_2/SiO_2/n-Si/p-Si$ solar in the element note done . Because , MgF_2 and SiO_2 of light break down indicator of air light break down of the indicator to the value of near _ Good optical the system harvest to do for above optical of the layer light break down

indicator of air light break down to the index , below optical layer while of silicon light break down to the indicator near to be need _

REFERENCES

1. Abbosbek Azizjon-o'g'li, A., & Nurillo Mo'ydinjon o'g, A. (2023). GORIZONTAL O 'QLI SHAMOL ENERGETIK QURILMALARINING ZAMONAVIY KONSTRUKSIYALARI.
2. M.O. Atajonov., S.J. Nimatov., A.I. Rahmatullayev. Formalization of the dynamics of the functioning of petrochemical complexes based on the theory of fuzzy sets and fuzzy logic. AIP Conference Proceedings, Published 2023-01-05. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1063/5.0112403>.
3. Sharobiddinov , S., & Mamarasulov, Q. (2023). QUYOSH HAVO ISITISH KOLLEKTORINI ENERGIYA SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISH. *Interpretation and Researches*, 1(8). ИЗВЛЕЧЕНО ОТ <https://interpretationandresearches.uz/index.php/iar/article/view/538>
4. Xolmirzaev, J. YU. (2022). ZONALNOE STROENIE KRISTALLOV V PRIBLIJENII MNOGOZONNOY (KEYNA) MODELI. *Oriental Renaissance: Innovative, educational, natural and social sciences*, 2(12), 748-753.
5. .ME Yulchiev, AAO Qodirov [Electricity Quality And Power Consumption In Low Power \(0.4 Kv\) Networks, THE AMERICAN JOURNAL OF ENGINEERING AND TECHNOLOGY \(TAJET\) SJIF-5.32 DOI-10.37547/tajet](#)
6. *Topvoldiyev, N. (2023). Quyosh havo isitish kollektorlarini o`rnatish va foydalaniz.*
7. Zuhritdinov Alisher Faraxidin o'g'li, Yo'lchiyev Mash'albek Erkinovich, Xakimov Temurbek Bahodirjon o'g'li. (2023). STUDY OF TEMPERATURE DEPENDENCE OF LINEAR EXPANSION COEFFICIENT OF SOLID BODIES. *INTERNATIONAL BULLETIN OF APPLIED SCIENCE AND TECHNOLOGY*, 3(5), 888–893. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7969053>

8. Д.Эгамов, М. Нурёғдиев. статья Повышение надёжности электроснабжения в местах проведение особо важных мероприятий. Научный журнал Инженерные решение №8(9) ноябрь 2019. г. Новосибирск.
9. Olimjonova, D., & Topvoldiyev, N. (2023). ANALYSIS OF HEAT STORAGE CAPACITY OF RESIDENTIAL BUILDINGS. Interpretation and Researches, 1(8).
10. Alijanov, D. D., & Axmadaliyev, U. A. (2021). APV Receiver In Automated Systems. The American Journal of Applied sciences.
11. Topvoldiyev, N. (2022). PHYSICAL AND TECHNICAL FUNDAMENTALS OF PHOTOELECTRIC SOLAR PANELS ENERGY. *Theoretical & Applied Science*.
12. Topvoldiyev, N. (2023). *Quyosh havo isitish kollektorlarini o`rnatish va foydalaniz*.
13. ME Yulchiev, AAO Qodirov [Electricity Quality And Power Consumption In Low Power \(0.4 Kv\) Networks, THE AMERICAN JOURNAL OF ENGINEERING AND TECHNOLOGY \(TAJET\) SJIF-5.32 DOI-10.37547/tajet](#)
14. NM Aripov, OA Qosimov MODELS AND METHODS FOR INCREASING THE EFFICIENCY OF INNOVATIVE RESEARCH 2 ...